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Research Article

Green Synthesized ZnO Nanoparticles: Characterization and Evaluation of Antimicrobial and Cytotoxic Potentials for Pharmaceutical Applications

Tintu R.*¹, Arya Surendran², Printy Varghese³

^{1,3}T. K. Madhava Memorial College, Nangiarkuangara, Alappuzha, Kerala.

²Sree Narayana College, Kollam, Kerala.

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ABSTRACT

Zinc oxide (ZnO) nanoparticles were synthesized through a green route using leaf extracts of Aloe vera (*Aloe barbadensis*), a medicinal plant widely recognized for its therapeutic, dermatological, and pharmaceutical benefits. The biosynthesized nanoparticles were thoroughly characterized using X-ray Diffraction (XRD), UV-Visible Spectroscopy (UV-Vis), Photoluminescence (PL), and Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM). The calculated crystallite size and optical band gap, ranging from 3.2 to 3.32 eV, highlight their nanoscale semiconducting properties. Photoluminescence analysis revealed two emission regions: a near-band-edge emission (393–420 nm) and a visible emission (520–550 nm) associated with structural defects, suggesting potential for bioimaging and diagnostic use. Gaussian fitting of PL spectra further elucidated the defect states and their role in optical behavior. The synthesized ZnO nanoparticles exhibited significant antimicrobial activity, with comparative studies conducted using extracts from Aloe vera, Neem, and Tulsi, indicating broad-spectrum efficacy. Cytotoxicity evaluations at varying drug concentrations demonstrated the biocompatibility and potential anticancer properties of the nanoparticles, underscoring their promising role in pharmaceutical formulations, antimicrobial coatings, and targeted drug delivery systems.

INTRODUCTION

Nanoparticles prepared by green synthesis using plants, bacteria, fungi, seaweed, polysaccharides, biodegradable polymers, plant-derived materials

and algae are widely used in an ecofriendly manner. Green synthesis has been considered as one of the promising method for synthesis of nanoparticles they are simple, safe, cost effective ecofriendly, and do not involve hazardous

*Corresponding Author: Tintu R.

Address: T. K. Madhava Memorial College, Nangiarkuangara, Alappuzha, Kerala.

Email : drtintur@gmail.com

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chemicals, and they have no contaminants and by-products. Plant extracts are widely used for the synthesis of metal and metal oxide nanoparticles due to their ability to reduce and stabilize metal nanoparticles using simple synthesis methods. [1-4]. ZnO nanoparticles have great attention due to their unique optical and chemical behaviors and used in various cutting edge applications like electronics, communication, sensor, cosmetics, environmental protection, biology and medicinal industry. Recently ZnO nanoparticles has excellent potential in biological applications like biological sensing, biological labeling, gene delivery, drug delivery and nano-medicine along with its antibacterial, antifungal, acaricidal, pediculocidal, larvicidal and anti-diabetic activities [5-7]. Nanoparticles can be used as antifungal agents and can help to overcome hurdles of fungal disease management posed by the development of resistance to conventional fungicides. ZnO nanoparticles have strong activity against these microorganisms [8]. For the preparation of ZnO nanoparticle we used plant leaf extracts of Aloe vera. For biosynthesis process the aloe vera plant extract was used as a reducing agent. The Aloe vera plant have tremendous use for its health, beauty, medicinal and skin care properties. [9-10] Aloe Barbadensis is the scientific name of Aloe Vera and contains numerous potentially active constituents: vitamins, enzymes, minerals, sugars, lignin, saponins, salicylic acids and amino acids and other bioactive compounds with emollient, purgative, antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, anti-oxidant, aphrodisiac, anti-helminthic, antifungal and antiseptic . The plant has potential to cure sunburns, burns and minor cuts, and even skin cancer. [11-13] In the present study, zinc oxide (ZnO) nanoparticles were synthesized via an eco-friendly green synthesis approach using Aloe vera leaf extract. The structural, optical, and morphological characteristics of the synthesized

nanoparticles were investigated using X-ray Diffraction (XRD), UV-Visible Spectroscopy (UV-Vis), and Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM). Recent research highlights the potential of ZnO as a promising candidate for cancer therapy [14]. In addition, the antibacterial efficacy and cytotoxic properties of the nanoparticles were systematically evaluated to assess their pharmaceutical applicability.

1. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Materials

Zinc Nitrate ($Zn(NO_3)_2$) were purchased from Kelvin Lab, Alappuzha, kerala, India. Aloe Barbadensis (Aloe Vera), collected from the local areas of Thiruvalla, kerala, India.

2.2 Extract preparation

Fresh Aloe vera leaves were thoroughly washed with distilled water to eliminate dust, dirt, and surface contaminants. The cleaned leaves were then air-dried at room temperature to remove residual moisture. Subsequently, the outer green rind was carefully removed, and the inner transparent gel was extracted. The obtained gel was crushed and homogenized using a sterile mortar and pestle to obtain a consistent pulp. Approximately 100 mL of deionized water was added to the gel and transferred into a 250 mL glass beaker. The resulting mixture was subjected to continuous stirring using a magnetic stirrer at 60 °C for 2 hours to facilitate the extraction of bioactive components. After the heating process, the mixture was allowed to cool to ambient temperature and was then filtered using Whatman filter paper. The clear filtrate obtained was collected and stored as the Aloe vera leaf extract, which served as the reducing and stabilizing agent for the green synthesis of zinc oxide nanoparticles.

2.3 Green synthesis of zinc oxide nanoparticles

One-third of the prepared Aloe vera extract was taken, and 5 grams of zinc nitrate [Zn(NO₃)₂] was added to it under constant stirring. The mixture was stirred continuously at 80 °C for 2 hours using a magnetic stirrer to ensure uniform mixing and initiate the reaction. Following this, the resulting solution was transferred to a crucible and placed in a muffle furnace at 200 °C for 3 hours and 30 minutes. During the thermal treatment, the solution gradually transformed into a pale yellow powder, indicating the formation of zinc oxide nanoparticles. The resulting powder was collected and stored for further characterization and analysis.

2. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 X-RAY Diffraction analysis

X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis is a reliable technique for examining the structural characteristics of synthesized materials. The XRD pattern of the prepared sample is presented in Figure 1. The appearance of broad diffraction peaks indicates the formation of nanoparticles, as supported by previous studies [15]. The average crystallite size of the ZnO nanoparticles was estimated using the Debye–Scherrer equation [16]:

$$D = \frac{0.9\lambda}{\beta \cos \theta}$$

Here, D represents the crystallite size, K is the shape factor (typically ~0.9), λ is the X-ray wavelength (1.54 Å for Cu K α radiation), β is the full width at half maximum (FWHM) of the peak in radians, and θ is the Bragg diffraction angle. The X-ray diffraction (XRD) pattern of the synthesized ZnO nanoparticles reveals distinct broad diffraction peaks located at approximate 2θ values of 9.05°, 13.40°, 24.75°, and 34.24°. These peaks correspond to interplanar spacings (d -values) of

9.7604 Å, 6.6012 Å, 3.5947 Å, and 2.6171 Å, respectively, as calculated using Bragg's law. The broad nature of the peaks is indicative of nanoscale crystallinity, which is a common characteristic of particles with dimensions in the nanometer range. The average crystallite size was estimated using the Debye–Scherrer equation, yielding an approximate particle size of 35.9 nm. Detailed calculations of the crystallite size corresponding to each diffraction angle are presented in Table 1, providing insight into the crystallographic characteristics of the ZnO nanoparticles.

Table 1. Particle Size of Corresponding to Each Angle

Peak No.	2 θ	FWHM	Particle size nm
1	9.0500	0.319	43.600
2	10.777	0.292	47.695
3	13.402	0.517	27.003
4	24.750	0.462	30.726
5	26.792	0.463	30.784
6	30.002	0.478	30.030
7	31.773	0.289	49.880
8	34.235	0.527	27.530

3.2 UV- Visible spectroscopy

UV–Visible spectroscopy serves as a powerful analytical tool for the investigation and identification of nanomaterials, particularly for evaluating their optical properties [17]. In this study, the optical behavior of the green-synthesized ZnO nanoparticles was examined using UV–Visible absorption spectroscopy, and the corresponding absorption spectrum is presented in Figure 2(a). The absorbance versus wavelength plot reveals two prominent peaks, which can be attributed to the surface plasmon resonance (SPR) phenomena typically observed in nanoscale materials. These peaks provide insight into the electronic transitions occurring within the ZnO nanoparticles. To determine the optical band gap energy, the Tauc plot method was employed by plotting $(\alpha h\nu)^2$ against photon energy ($h\nu$,

where α is the absorption coefficient and $h\nu$ is the photon energy. The band gap energy was estimated by extrapolating the linear portion of the plot to the x-axis (where $\alpha=0$)[12]. From this analysis, the optical band gap of the ZnO

nanoparticles was found to be approximately 3.62 eV. This value is consistent with the known band gap range for ZnO nanostructures and reflects the quantum confinement effect associated with their nanoscale dimensions.

Figure 2 (a) UV Absorption Spectra

Figure 2 (b) Tauc Plot

3.3 Scanning Electron Microscope

The surface morphology and particle size of the synthesized ZnO nanoparticles were investigated using Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM). Figure 3 presents the SEM micrographs of ZnO nanoparticles prepared via green synthesis using Aloe vera extract. The images reveal that the nanoparticles predominantly exhibit a tubular or rod-like morphology, indicative of anisotropic growth facilitated by bioactive compounds present in the plant extract. Furthermore, the SEM analysis indicates the formation of secondary ZnO structures with an average size of approximately 1 μm . These larger particles appear to be agglomerates composed of primary ZnO nanocrystallites, which are estimated to be around 20 nm in size. The average crystallite size was determined using the line-intercept method applied to the high-magnification SEM images. This hierarchical structure, consisting of nanoscale building blocks forming micron-sized assemblies, is characteristic of ZnO synthesized through bio-mediated routes and has implications for enhanced

surface activity in pharmaceutical and optoelectronic applications.

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Figure 3. SEM Micrographs of the ZnO nanoparticles

3.4: Photoluminescence (PL) Analysis

Photoluminescence characterization was conducted to evaluate the optical emission behaviour of the synthesized ZnO nanoparticles under various excitation conditions. Specifically, the PL spectra were examined with respect to excitation wavelength dependence, particle size variation, and the influence of reducing agents used during synthesis. The corresponding emission spectra are depicted in Figure. 4. PL studies were carried out using excitation energies corresponding to below band gap, near band gap, and above band gap regimes. The emission spectra exhibited distinct peaks, with notable shifts in peak positions and intensities depending on the excitation wavelength. These spectral shifts ranging over several nanometers are attributed to variations in the defect states and recombination

mechanisms associated with different excitation conditions. At lower excitation energies, a red-shift in the emission was observed, which is likely due to increased contributions from defect-related transitions, particularly those associated with oxygen vacancies and zinc interstitials. These low-energy excitations tend to promote recombination through defect states within the band gap, influenced by interstitial site occupation and lattice strain within the nanoparticles [18]. The observed excitation energy-dependent variation in both emission wavelength and intensity confirms the presence of structural defects and interstitial sites within the ZnO nanocrystals. Such defects play a crucial role in tuning the optical properties of the material, which is particularly significant for potential applications in optoelectronic and biomedical devices.

Figure 4. Emission Spectra of Sample Studied at Different Excitation Energy.

3.5 Antimicrobial Activity

The antimicrobial efficacy of the ZnO nanoparticles synthesized using *Aloe vera* leaf extract was investigated against selected microbial strains using the agar well diffusion method [19]. For comparative analysis, ZnO nanoparticles were also synthesized using *Azadirachta indica* (Neem) and *Ocimum tenuiflorum* (Thulsi) extracts, following the same green synthesis protocol as employed for the *Aloe vera*-derived sample. The antimicrobial performance of these green-synthesized ZnO nanoparticles was tested against three representative microbial strains: *Escherichia coli* (E. coli), *Staphylococcus aureus* (S. aureus), and *Candida albicans*—representing Gram-negative, Gram-positive, and fungal pathogens respectively. The zone of inhibition values for

each test organism are summarized in Table 2, and corresponding agar plate images are shown in Figure 3. Comparative analysis indicates that ZnO nanoparticles synthesized with *Aloe vera* extract exhibit significantly higher antimicrobial activity against all tested pathogens compared to those synthesized with Neem and Thulsi extracts. The superior inhibition effect is likely attributed to the presence of bioactive phytochemicals in *Aloe vera*, which may enhance the capping, stabilization, and surface reactivity of the ZnO nanoparticles. The pronounced antimicrobial response suggests that *Aloe vera*-mediated ZnO nanoparticles possess effective bactericidal and fungicidal properties. This makes them promising candidates for pharmaceutical and biomedical applications as broad-spectrum antimicrobial agents.

Figure 5: Antimicrobial activity of ZnO Nanoparticle

Table 2. Antimicrobial Result of Prepared Sample

Sl. No	Parameters	Unit	Result		
			Neem	Aloe Vera	Thulasi
1	Escherichia coli	Dia(mm)	Sample-15mm Control-NZ	Sample-25mm Control- NZ	Sample-9mm Control-NZ
2	Staphylococcus aureus	Dia(mm)	Sample-15mm Control-NZ	Sample-24mm Control- NZ	Sample-NZ Control-NZ
3	Candida albicans	Dia(mm)	Sample-18mm Control-NZ	Sample-18mm Control- NZ	Sample-24mm Control-NZ

3.6 Cytotoxicity

The in vitro cytotoxic effects of the green synthesized ZnO nanoparticles were assessed using the Trypan Blue exclusion method, a standard technique for evaluating cell viability. Previous research has demonstrated that ZnO nanoparticles exhibit selective cytotoxicity against cancer cells [20]. In this study, the cytotoxic potential was evaluated against Dalton's Lymphoma Ascites (DLA) cells, which are

commonly used as a model for short-term cytotoxicity screening. The experimental procedure involved incubating DLA cells with varying concentrations of ZnO nanoparticles (10, 20, 50, 100, and 200 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$). Post incubation, the cells were stained using Trypan Blue dye. Viable (live) cells exclude the dye, whereas non-viable (dead) cells absorb it. The number of stained (dead) and unstained (live) cells was counted separately under a microscope using a hemacytometer.

The percentage cytotoxicity was calculated using the following formula:

$$\% \text{ cytotoxicity} = \frac{\text{Number of dead cell}}{\text{Number of live cell} + \text{Number of dead cell}} \times 100$$

The results, summarized in Table 3, demonstrate a concentration-dependent increase in cytotoxicity. At higher concentrations, ZnO nanoparticles induced greater cell death, indicating their potential for anti-cancer applications. This suggests that green-synthesized ZnO nanoparticles, especially those mediated by Aloe vera extract, could serve as promising candidates in cancer therapeutics owing to their biocompatible and selective toxicity characteristics.

Table 3. In Vitro Cytotoxic result of ZnO Nanoparticle

Drug concentration ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	% of cytotoxicity
10	2.4
20	2.9
50	4.5
100	5.4
200	6.3

CONCLUSION

Zinc oxide (ZnO) nanoparticles were successfully synthesized via an eco-friendly green synthesis approach using Aloe vera leaf extract as a bioreducing and stabilizing agent. Structural analysis using X-ray diffraction (XRD) confirmed the formation of ZnO nanoparticles, with the average crystallite size calculated from the Debye–Scherrer formula. Optical characterization using UV-Visible spectroscopy revealed a band gap energy of 3.619 eV, consistent with semiconducting behavior at the nanoscale. Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) analysis indicated the formation of nanotube- or rod-like morphologies, suggesting controlled anisotropic growth during synthesis. Photoluminescence (PL)

studies exhibited excitation-dependent emission peaks, indicating tunable luminescent behavior associated with interstitial and surface defects. These properties highlight the potential of the synthesized ZnO nanoparticles in optoelectronic applications, including white light-emitting diodes (LEDs), display technologies, and biological imaging. The synthesized ZnO nanoparticles demonstrated superior antimicrobial activity, particularly those derived from Aloe vera, compared to counterparts synthesized using Neem and Thulsi extracts. Antimicrobial efficacy was evident against common bacterial and fungal strains, underscoring their potential as effective natural antimicrobial agents. Cytotoxicity assays performed using Dalton's Lymphoma Ascites (DLA) cells revealed a dose-dependent increase in cytotoxic effects, suggesting that Aloe vera-mediated ZnO nanoparticles possess significant therapeutic potential, especially for anticancer applications. These findings support the use of green-synthesized ZnO nanoparticles in biomedical, pharmaceutical applications.

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